

ISic1007

I.Sicily inscription 1007

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Catacomb of S.Giovanni

Coordinates**Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa, Museo Archeologico
Regionale Paolo Orsi, inventory 120

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. αἰ μακάριε παρθένοι
2. Φωτίνη κέ Φιλουμένη
3. ἐνθάδε κῖντε σεμνέ ἀγνέ
4. παρθένοι ζήσασε βίου κα
5. λοῦ ἢ μιζοτέρα ἐτῶν
6. π · καὶ ἢ μικροτέρα ἐτῶ[ν]
7. πδ ὀρκοῦ σε κατὰ τοῦ θε
8. οὔ τοῦ παντοκράτορος
9. μηδένα αὐτὰς σκῦλέ
10. □ ποτε □

Apparatus

Text of IG with slight changes based on Kaibel's diplomatic transcription

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492634

EDCS 39102161

PHI 140485

Bibliography

Kaibel, G. 1890. Inscriptiones Graecae Siciliae et Italiae, additis graecis Galliae Hispaniae, Britanniae, Germaniae inscriptionibus. *Inscriptiones Graecae consilio et auctoritate Academiae Litterarum Regiae Borussicae Editae. Volumen XIV.* Berlin. At 14.0187 (<https://clio.columbia.edu/catalog/6873760>)

Agnello, S.L. 1953. Silloge di iscrizioni paleocristiane della Sicilia. Rome. At no.15

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